

“A STUDY OF THE ROLE OF SCHOOL MANAGEMENT COMMITTEE IN SCHOOL DEVELOPMENT.”

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Introduction

Primary Education is one of the main and important media for personality development, Social transformation and also for national development. Therefore for the above said reasons, in the state of Maharashtra various schemes and programmes are being run and operated, with an aim and intention to provide Primary educational facilities to all children and thereby to give them, good quality education. The Central Government implemented a programme called as Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan to implement this scheme to encourage students, educational training programme at State level and also a participation of the Local Community in School Management was planned.

As per the G.R. P R E /1087/417959/(8424)/Primary Education-1, of 7th September, 1991, the formation of Village Education Committee has been made, with an aim and motive at national level to provide pre-primary education, Primary Education, literacy, and planning of the continuous education, and to make co-ordination and control of these things and to make active participation in the Local Social Educational process. Nevertheless, the Government Authority as per their passed Notification No. G.R. P R E-2001/(2769)/Primary Education -1 of dated 16th April, 2001, has taken decision to make all the concerned Surpunch of the Grampanchayat Village Education Committee an authorized President and also for the re-constitution or re-construction of the Village Educational Committee, by making co-ordination between village educational committee, to have formal or informal educational control and supervision at local level and according to that, the formation and constitution of the Village Educational Committee has been made for the purpose of Management of the Primary School in each village.

As per the 86th Constitutional Amendment of the year 2002, as per the Para 21(a) the right of education has been included in the Basic Fundamental Rights by the Central Government. According to that, all children between age group from 6 to 14 the Central Government has passed the Law, Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009 (No.35-2009), as per that the free and compulsory education shall be provided, and information about the said act and it's coverage under this act, has been published in the Gazette of the Government of India, dated 27.08.2009. And also, the concerned Government of India in their Govt. Gazette dated 16.02.2010 has mentioned or stated that the said provisions under the said Act, the said should be applicable and to be followed all over the India within effect from 01.04.2010, (excluding Jammu and Kashmir State).

Through the media of Primary Education, the important values like equality, social justice and democracy and establishment of justice in human society, can be achieved. For the sake of this reason the said act has been implemented. Therefore the Government has accepted the responsibility of providing free and compulsory primary education to all the children of age group from 6 to 14 years and also to these children to give the admission in the school, and also taken responsibility to maintain the regular attendance of the concerned students in the school and to see that they should complete their primary education.

To have public participation in the educational development the formation of the Village Educational Committee, Ward Educational Committee, or for the private schools School Committee has been formed. The said committees are playing an important role in the physical and educational development. For the same the Government has granted some financial rights, and responsibility and also some

liabilities to all the concerned school committee. The work performed and implemented by the Committee at great extent are found to be useful for the development of the school.

It is compulsory and essential to establish school management committee before 30th day of September, 2009 for all the schools, except unaided school. This has to be done as per the Right to Education, Free and Compulsory Education of Child Act, of 2009.

As per the provision of the above said Act the control of work of school is handed over to this committee. School Management Committee was established after a change in work and structure of Village Education Committee, Ward Education Committee and School Committee.

It is necessary and essential to study the work performed by the School Management Committee, which has been formed for full-fledged development of the primary school.

Need and Importance of Research

The personality of child comes into shape through the medium of home, environment and school. When the personality and image of child is taking shape in his personality, during that period the concerned Guardian of the said child are taking the care of the said child, and also in similar way the teacher of his school is taking care of the said child in the school, in which the child is taking education to therefore due to the said reason, if the Teachers of the school and guardians at home, make joint efforts for the concerned child, in that case, the personality of the child will flourish like a flower, especially for those schools, in which there is participation of the Guardian of the child, in which the child is taking his education.

In accordance to the provisions laid in the Right to Education, Free and Compulsory Education of Child Act, of 2009, of Part 4, Section 21 of the same, the formation of the School Management Committee has been made in each primary school. After the application of the said Act, in all the school, the School Management committee has been formed except unaided school.

As per the Government Resolution, the School Management Committee has been formed in Zilla Parishad and in Municipal Corporation Schools in Thane District.

The necessary change has been made to some extent in the structure and work of Village Education Committee, and Ward Education Committee. And also necessary change has been made up to some extent in the structure and work of the School Management according to School Development. The said formation of such type of Committee is to be made, within 3 months, from the date of commencement or starting of the academic year and also the re-structuring of the said Committee has to be done, after every 2 years.

In the present research, according to provision of Right to Education, Free and Compulsory Education of Child Act, of 2009, a study of role of School Management Committee in School Development, which is established for School Management as well as a Comparison of work of School Management between Zilla Parishad School and Municipal Corporation School will be done by the researcher.

Review of Related Literature

1. Pant Y. R. (1984) Ph. D. Punjab University. Participation of parents in education, a study of social and collective contribution of rural parents in Nepal.

Summary: Objectives – To see the participation of society in qualitative development of school in rural area. To study different types of participation of public in education field. Finding – All the People from different community level are not participated in education. IL literal and poor people got less benefit of educational facilities. There is more importance of society contribution for qualitative educational process.

2. Sullivan (1985) Ph. D. Thailand - A study of participation of parents in the school activity in Thailand.

Summary : - The main objective of research is to study the parent's participation in secondary school education. Finding – Highly educated parents are taking participation in school activity. Parents in urban area takes part in school activities more than rural area.

3. Dr. Kalpana Chitre (Ph.D. 2003) “A comparative study of small meal scheme and its impact in Brihan Mumbai Municipal corporation Primary School and Thane Municipal Corporation Primary School.”

Summary: The main objective of this research was to find out present real position of this small meal scheme and the impact on the students. For conducting this research total 140 schools were selected from Brihan Mumbai and Thane District of this region, total 70 schools from each district were taken. Finding shows rise of attendance of students in these schools. To some extent the hunger of the students of the Mumbai School have been met compared to the students who are taking their education in Thane school.

4. Dr. Gopinath Patil (Ph.D. 2004) “Role of Gram Shikshan Samiti in the universalization of Primary Education”.

Summary: The main objective of this research was to make a study of the role of Gram Shikshan Samiti in the attendance, stagnation, schools programs and other facilities. In this research 300 Gram Shikshan Samitis were selected from Murbad and Shahpur talukas. Survey method used for data collection. Findings- Gram Shikshan Samiti gave special attention towards enrollment. The guardians of the students were aware of the facilities which are being provided in the school. The members of Gram Shikshan Samiti are providing educational study materials, books and other related essential things to the students. Different activities and programmes are implemented for the universalization of Primary Education.

5. Chobhe Ravindra, (2006) Ph. D. Pune University. A critical study of Government of Maharashtra notification dated June 1997 regarding parent teacher association functioning and its remedies at secondary School in Ahmednagar and its recommendation.

Summary: – The main objective of research is to study the time to time circulars regarding parent teacher association and total number students in 100% schools. The implementation of parent teacher association is not done as per the guidelines of government circular.

6. Patil Sushma (2009) Ph. D. Pune University – To find out the reasons of stagnation and dropout of girl students in adolescent stage in Government post public Ashram School in Tribal Nandurbar district.

Summary: – The main objective of this research is to suggest facilities after a review of girl student in adolescent stage in Government post public Ashram School in Tribal Nandurbar district. Finding – There is total 40% stagnation and 80% dropout of girl student in Std. V to VIII. There is total 57% dropout at Std. V due to child labour. So there is big ratio of parent's poverty and nescience about education. The shifting of families from one place to another is 12%.

7. Dr Pawar Bharat (2014), Ph. D. – A study of society participation in development of Zilla Parishad primary schools in Thane district in Maharashtra state.

Summary:- the main objective of the research is to study the present status of School Management committee, parent teacher association and mother parent association in school development and suggest the remedies for their strengthening. Finding- The mother parent association is established in school but there is regular meeting. The attendance of members is irregular. There is a discussion of academic quality improvement of students in meeting. **Statement of Research Problem**

“A Study the Role of School Management Committee in School Development.”

Aim of Research

To Study the Role of School Management Committee in School Development.

Variables of Research

Dependent Variable- School Development.

Independent Variable- School Management Committee.

Conceptual and Operational Definition

1. School Development: By using Physical facilities, financial facilities and Human resources to increase the standard of educational quality and educational development of the school.

The infrastructural basic facilities of the school should be provided e.g. School Building, Toilet Facilities, Drinking water facility Electrification, Sports and Playground, Library, Kitchen facilities and other such essential facilities and amenities. To make supervision over the proper distribution and utilization of various funds received by schools, which are coming under the financial rights. To increase the standard of Educational quality and Educational development of school by making use of duties like 100% enrollment, 100% attendance, to bring and retain the children who are outside the school and handicapped children in the main stream of education, Right to Education, Free and Compulsory Education of Child Act, of 2009, midday meal scheme, control on school and administration work.

2. School Management Committee: In accordance to the provisions of Right to Education, Free and Compulsory Education of Child Act, of 2009, as per the Section 21 of part-4 therein, in each primary school, the required School Management Committee has been formed before the date of 30th September, 2010.

Before the date of 30th September, 2010, the establishment of the School Management Committee in the Zilla Parishad Primary Schools and Municipal Corporation School situated in Thane District for the development of the school and to keep control on school as well as for administrative work.

Objectives of Research

1. To study the role of School Management Committee in the preparation of School Development Plan in the Primary School.
2. To study the role of School Management Committee in the Utilization of received funds, Annual income and its Expenditures and to maintain the Record in the Primary School.
3. To study the role of School Management Committee in the Controlling Work in the Primary School.
4. To study the role of School Management Committee about Right to Education of Child Act.
5. To study the role of School Management Committee to maintain 100% Enrollment and 100% Attendance of the students in the Primary School.
6. To study the role of School Management Committee to bring and retain the outside children and physically challenged children in the main stream of Education.
7. To study the role of School Management Committee in the Midday meal scheme in the Primary School.
8. To study the role of School Management Committee in the provisions of the basic physical facilities in the Primary School.
9. To study the role of School Management Committee in the administrative work in the Primary School.
10. To study the role of School Management Committee about the School building, other school related construction and repairing.

11. To compare the structure and work performed of School Management committee in Zilla Parishad Primary School with Municipal Corporation Primary School.

Hypothesis of Research

1. There is no significant difference in means of participation while preparation of School Development Plan between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School.
2. There is no significant difference in the work of the Utilization of received funds Annual income and its Expenditures and to maintain the record between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School.
3. There is no significant difference in the work of School control between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School.
4. There is no significant difference in the work of the Right to Education Act for children between the School Management Committee of the Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School.
5. There is no significant difference in the work of 100% Enrollment and 100% Attendance between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School.
6. There is no significant difference in the work in bringing and retaining the outside children and physically challenged children in the main stream of education between School Management committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School.
7. There is no significant difference in the work of Midday meal scheme between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School.
8. There is no significant difference in the work of providing basic physical facilities between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School.
9. There is no significant difference in the administrative work between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School.
10. There is significant difference observed in the work of school building, other school related construction and repairing work between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School Municipal Corporation Primary School.
11. There is no significant difference in the structure of School Management Committee between Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School.

Scope and Limitation of Research

In the present research the researcher has only taken Thane district of Mumbai Region into her consideration. From urban area, Thane city and Kalyan-Dombivali city as well as from rural area Kalyan and Ambernath blocks have been taken into consideration. Other School Management Committees have not been taken into consideration.

In this research only School Management Committee of Marathi medium primary schools has been taken into consideration. School Management Committee of Hindi, English, Urdu, Guajarati and other medium primary school are not included.

Researcher has taken into Consideration School Management Committee of schools from local governing body of Municipal Corporation Primary School of Thane and Kalyan-Dombivali city as well as Zilla Parishad Primary Schools of Kalyan and Ambernath blocks of Thane District. School

Management Committee of Zilla Parishad of other blocks and Municipal Corporation Primary Schools of other School Management Committee are not included.

Methodology of Research

The Present research is a comparative study of role of School Management Committee in School Development from Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School. A descriptive method has been used to collect data about role and work of School Management Committee as well as to compares the role of School Management Committee between Zilla Parishad Primary Schools and Municipal Corporation Primary Schools.

Sample

60% Primary Schools of Municipal Corporation from Thane and Kalyan-Dombivali , which are '54' and '30' vice versa as well as 60% Primary Schools of Zilla Parishad from Kalyan and Ambernath blocks which are '73' and '68' vice versa are selected. In this way total School Management Committee of 225 schools are included in the study of present research.

Simple random sampling technique has been used for sample selection.

Tools of Research

Following Research Tools has been used for essential data collection in present research.

1. Questionnaire - (1) The President of School Management Committee (Guardian).
(2) Head Master (Secretary)
2. Interview - (1) Block Educational Officer and Administrative Officer.
(2) Kendra Pramukh (Head of Cluster Resource Centre)
3. Observation - Meeting of School Management Committee.

All above Research tools has been used by researcher, which are self-made.

Techniques for Data Analysis

The following statistical techniques have been used for data analysis of present research.

1. Descriptive Analysis
 - Measures of Central tendencies
 1. Mean
 2. Median
 3. Mode
 - Measures of variabilities
 1. Standard deviation
 2. Skewness
 3. Kurtosis
2. Inferential Analysis
 1. 't' test
 2. Mean

Major Findings and Conclusions

1. There is significant difference observed in participation of School Management Committee in participation while preparation of School Development Plan between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School at 0.05 level. As per the mean value we can state that School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School is more active than School Management Committee of Municipal Corporation Primary School.

2. There is no significant difference observed in the work of the Utilization of received funds Annual income and its Expenditures and to maintain the record between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School. It means both SMC are doing equal work regarding monitoring of received fund, to give permission for utilization of received fund/grant and checking of account /expenditure of record.
3. There is no significant difference observed in the work of School control between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School. It means SMC both are doing equal work regarding school visit, checking of educational quality of school, supervision of actual condition of physical infrastucture, to review, teachers irregularity, misbehaviour and daily absenteism.
4. There is significant difference observed in the work of the Right to Education Act for children between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School at 0.01 level. As per the mean value we can state that School Management Committee of Municipal Corporation Primary School is more active than School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School regarding age appropriate admission, solution of problem related to RTE 2009 under the guidance of experts.
5. There is no significant difference observed in the work of 100% Enrollment and 100% Attendance between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School. It means both are doing equal work regarding survey of 100% Enrollment children between 6 to 14 year age group, taking daily review about absent students.
6. There is significant difference observed in the work in bringing and retaining the outside children and physically challenged children in the main stream of education between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School at 0.01 level. As per the mean value we can state that School Management Committee of Municipal Corporation Primary School is more active than School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School regarding survey of out of school children, to find reason of absenteeism of out of school children, to make facilities available for Children With Special Needs.
7. There is significant difference observed in the work of Midday meal scheme between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School at 0.01 level. As per the mean value we can state that School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School is more active than School Management Committee of Municipal Corporation Primary School for trying to give nutritious mid day meal, to check the taste register, selection of proper person for cooking mid day meal.
8. There is significant difference observed in the work of providing basic physical facilities between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School at 0.01 level. As per the mean value we can state that School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School is more active than School Management Committee of Municipal Corporation Primary School with respect to availabilities of basic facilities through public/ society participation, to collect the fund from rich and generous people in village/city.
9. There is no significant difference observed in the administrative work between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School. It means both are doing equal work regarding attending daily meetings of School Management Committee, to solve the problems of Teachers, to help for build relation between school and society.

10. There is significant difference observed in the work of school building, other school related construction and repairing between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School at 0.01 level. Observed difference in work of School Management Committee regarding proper utilization of maintainance and repairing work grant, to pay attention for casual repairing in school.

11. There is no significant difference observed in the structure of School Management Committee between School Management Committee of Zilla Parishad Primary School and Municipal Corporation Primary School. It is observed that the structure of SMC as per the Right to Education Act 2009 is same in both authorities.

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